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ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
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SPECIAL ISSUE 1

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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Nozima Tokhirzhonovna Mavlyanova**Nazifa Valievna Agzamova**Department of Family Medicine №2, Clinical Pharmacology,
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EVALUATION OF THE USE OF ANTIBACTERIAL DRUGS** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7797038>**ABSTRACT**

A retrospective clinical and economic analysis was carried out in two departments of the TashPMI clinic to study the frequency of prescribing antibacterial drugs using the ABC analysis method. The data of bacteriological seeding of these patients for sensitivity were analyzed and the quantitative composition of pathogens in pathologies of the respiratory tract in children under 5 years of age was studied.

Keywords: antibacterial drugs, children's diseases, abc analysis, microbes.

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ АНТИБАКТЕРИАЛЬНЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Проведен ретроспективный клинико-экономический анализ в двух отделениях клиники ТашПМИ для изучения кратности назначения антибактериальных препаратов по методике ABC-анализа. Проведен анализ данных бактериологического посева этих больных на чувствительность и изучен количественный состав возбудителей при патологиях дыхательных путей у детей до 5 лет.

Ключевые слова: антибактериальные препараты, болезни детей младшего возраста, abc анализ, микрофлора посева.

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ANTIBAKTERIAL DORILARNING BAHOLASHDA KLINIK-IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI**ANNOTATSIYA.**

ToshPTI klinikasining ikkita bo'limida ABC-tahlil usuli yordamida antibakterial preparatlarni buyurish chastotasini o'rganish maqsadida retrospektiv klinik-iqtisodiy tahlil o'tkazildi. Ushbu bemorlarni sezgirlik uchun bakteriologik ekish ma'lumotlari tahlil qilindi va 5 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarda nafas olish yo'llari patologiyalarida patogenlarning miqdoriy tarkibi o'rganildi.

Kalit so'zlar: antibakterial dori vositalari, yosh bolalar kasalliklari, abc tahlili, ekuv mikroflorasi.

Introduction. In many literature data, it is noted that in medical institutions, in matters of providing medicines, the class of antibacterial drugs is also of no small importance. To assess exactly how much antibacterial drugs were used, accounting for their purchase is used. The cost of antimicrobial therapy is 30% of the budget of medical institutions. The most important section of the rational use of drugs is the introduction of guidelines, protocols, standards for the diagnosis and treatment of diseases.

Protocols and standards are not a complete technological form, they should be considered as a dynamic methodological system that requires constant revision and change. This provision is especially relevant in relation to antibacterial drugs, since their use is associated with antibiotic resistance, the formularies of this group of drugs should be regularly reviewed in accordance with the infection monitoring data of a particular medical institution. The development and application of accurate diagnostic schemes and approaches to the treatment of patients will make it possible to carry out diagnostics, including differential, in the shortest possible time, and to choose a plan for managing a particular patient. Starting points should be the clinical presentation, the spectrum of suspected infectious agents, and the antibiotic resistance profile of the particular hospital. A comprehensive clinical and economic analysis of drugs usually includes frequency analysis, ABC and DDD methodologies. Clinical and economic analysis allows you to prioritize among purchased drugs, limits the possibility of uncontrolled use of drugs that do not belong to the category of vital importance. It also contributes to improving the quality of medical care and the main task of clinical and economic analysis is to optimize the technologies for the acquisition and use of drugs, expand their range and quality, which in general will improve the level of medical care for the population.

Materials and methods. The material for the study was the case histories of children with a hospitalized diagnosis of community-acquired pneumonia, acute and recurrent bronchitis, bronchopneumonia in two departments of the TashPMI clinic, aged from 3 months to 5 years, treated with antibacterial drugs in the period March-May 2022. The main method of study is ABC analysis, as well as frequency analysis of not only antibacterial drugs, but also their pathogens with the detection of pathogen sensitivity to drugs.

Results. Analysis of the microflora and its sensitivity to antibacterial drugs, based on the results of bacteriological studies conducted in the bacteriological laboratory of the TashPMI clinic in two departments in 2022. showed that different susceptibility of pathogens of the same species, family, genus was determined in the departments. This problem was caused by the presence of hospital strains of pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microorganisms. The obtained data on the sensitivity of microorganisms make it possible to determine the list of antibacterial drugs for empirical (initial) therapy for each department. In the study institution, among the departments with a high consumption of antibacterial drugs, of course, there are intensive care units, surgical departments, but we chose the department of pulmonology and the department of children from 3 months to 3 years as the most significant for optimizing antibiotic therapy from early childhood and preventing resistance in children from an early age of life, as well as reducing child and infant mortality. In addition, it is the correct and rational use and analysis of the use of antibacterial drugs in childhood that guarantees the success of their use in later life, which can serve as the use of reservoir antibiotics in difficult life-threatening minutes. Based on the results of the analysis of the microbial landscape, lists of antibacterial drugs were compiled, to which the microorganisms that make up the leading microflora in each profile department are highly sensitive, and which can be

used to conduct empirical (starting) antibiotic therapy. Preparations were taken into account, to which the sensitivity of these microorganisms was over 90% and over 75%. The assessment of antibiotic activity was determined as follows: 100-95% inhibition was assessed as absolute activity, up to 75% - good. Antibacterial drugs with an activity against the alleged pathogen of 74% or less cannot be prescribed empirically, without determining the antibiogram of the microorganism. In the structure of microorganisms, etiologically significant pathogens were determined. The greatest concern was caused by the appearance of pathogenic microorganisms, with signs of hospital strains, and especially with polyresistance. Monitoring was defined as a system for tracking the species composition of the microflora that stands out in a certain subdivision, with a certain nosological form and its sensitivity to antibiotics. The structure of microorganisms sown from patients in departments with increased consumption of antibacterial drugs and the sensitivity of the leading microflora to antibiotics were studied. An analysis of the results in the pulmonology department showed that pathogens were included in the category of the leading microflora *Enterobacter* spp.: *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. This flora has a high sensitivity to aminoglycosides, fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin), third-generation cephalosporins (ceftriaxone, ceftazidime). Despite the fact that *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris* are inferior to *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in terms of seeding frequency, nevertheless, they retain high sensitivity to the above groups of drugs, including antipseudomonal drugs cefoperazone, cefepime. The recommendations for the department clearly defined drugs for empirical therapy. Regarding gram-positive microflora - *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, we see high susceptibility to oxacillin, a marker of susceptibility to all beta-lactam antibiotics. *Enterococcus durans*, had high sensitivity to ceftriaxone, cefepime, imipenem, rifampicin, vancomycin. The results obtained allow us to determine the range of drugs for initial therapy. It was also possible to use third-generation cephalosporins (ceftriaxone, ceftazidime), other drugs with high activity against microflora were classified as second-line or reserve drugs. The reserve included drugs with the widest spectrum of action or drugs that have no analogues in relation to resistant strains, which were also included in the category of expensive drugs, but according to the results of a clinical and economic analysis. In the department of emergency surgery, the predominantly sown microflora included *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Enterobacter aerogenes* with a high degree of sensitivity to aminoglycosides (amikacin, gentamicin), ciprofloxacin.

Discussion. Uncontrolled outbreaks of acute respiratory diseases in the winter bring great economic damage and require emergency mobilization of health service reserves. The ability to predict their development would allow optimizing the work of medical institutions. Scientists from the UK have proposed using data on the sale of drugs to the public as a signal system that predicts the emergence of a new outbreak. Researchers suggest that a significant increase in the level of resistance of strains *Escherichia coli* possibly due to excessive use of the antibiotic in hospitals or by the population itself. It should be noted that pharmacies are located very close to the medical center, where it is enough to simply buy any antibacterial drug without a prescription.

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